

Jobstress of Teachers Working In Special Schools

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Abstract:A special school is a school catering for students who have special educational needs due to serve learning difficulties, physical disabilities or behavioural problems. Special schools may be specifically designed, staffed and resourced to provide appropriate special education for children with additional needs. A Special school is a school for children who have some kind of serious physical or mental problem. The present study examines the job stress of teachers working in special schools. The sample of the study comprised of 156 special school teachers working in aided and private special schools in Tirunelveli district, Tamilnadu. Simple random method was used to select the sample from the population. Survey method was used to collect data. The findings revealed that there is significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to locality of special school teachers, qualification and work experience of special school teachers.

Key words: Job stress, special school, special school teachers.

I. Introduction

Job stress can be defined as the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker. It arises when demands exceed abilities, while job-related strains are reactions or outcomes resulting from the experience of stress. Excessively high workloads, with unrealistic deadlines making people feel rushed, under pressure and overwhelmed. In sufficient workloads, making people feel that their skills are being under used. A lack of control over work activities and interpersonal support or poor working relationships leading to a sense of isolation. The investigator focused on job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to selected variables.

Objectives of the study

- To find out the level of job stress of teachers working in special schools.
- To find out the significant difference, if any, in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to personal variables namely gender, locality of special school teachers and marital status.
- To find out the significant difference, if any, in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to institutional variables namely type of the school and locality of the school.
- To find out the significant difference, if any, in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to familial variable namely type of family.
- To find out the significant difference, if any, in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to professional variables namely qualification and work experience of special school teachers.

Hypotheses of the study

- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to male and female.
- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to rural and urban.

- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to married and unmarried.
- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to aided and private schools.
- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to rural and urban.
- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to nuclear and joint family.
- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to experience.
- To find out there is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to qualification.

II. Methodology

Survey method was selected to evaluate the job stress of teachers working in special schools.

Population and sample

The population for the present study comprises of special school teachers working in and around Tirunelveli educational district, Tamilnadu. The Sample consists of 156 special school teachers randomly selected from various special schools in and around Tirunelveli educational district, Tamilnadu.

Tool used

The tool used in this study was Job stress scale developed by F.J.Lilly (2008).

Statistical techniques used

Percentage analysis, t-test and F-test.

Data Analysis

Objective 1: Level of job stress of teachers working in special schools

Table 1

Level of job stress of teachers working in special schools

Negative		Neutral		Positive	
N	%	N	%	N	%
19	12.2	112	71.8	25	16.0

The above table shows that three-fifth of the special school teachers have neutral job stress.

Objective 2: Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to personal variables

Table 2

Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to personal variables

The above table shows that more than three-fifth of special school teachers are having their job stress

Personal Variables	Category	Negative		Neutral		Positive	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Gender	Female	16	12.9	90	72.6	18	14.5
	Male	3	9.4	22	68.8	7	21.9
Locality	Rural	12	15.2	57	72.2	10	12.7
	Urban	7	9.1	55	71.4	15	19.5
Marital Status	Married	14	11	91	71.7	22	17.3
	Unmarried	5	17.2	21	72.4	3	10.3

with regard to personal variables namely gender, locality and marital status.

Objective 3: Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to institutional variables

Table 3

Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to institutional variables

Institutional Variables	Category	Negative		Neutral		Positive	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Type of School	Aided	10	10.5	66	69.5	19	20
	Private	9	14.8	46	75.4	6	9.8
Locality of School	Rural	12	15.2	57	72.2	10	12.7
	Urban	7	9.1	55	71.4	15	19.5

The above table shows that more than three-fifth of special school teachers are having their job stress with regard to institutional variables namely type and locality of school.

Objective 4: Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to familial variables

Table 4

Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to familial variables

Familial Variable	Category	Negative		Neutral		Positive	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Types of family	Nuclear	11	12.5	59	67.8	17	19.5
	Joint	8	11.6	53	76.8	8	11.6

The above table shows that more than three-fifth of special school teachers are having job stress with regard to types of family.

Objective 5: Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to professional variables

Table 5

Level of job stress of special school teachers with regard to professional variables

Professional Variables	Category	Negative		Neutral		Positive	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Qualification	D.T.Ed	6	12	29	68.5	15	30
	UG WITH B.Ed	6	10	49	71.7	5	8.3
	PG WITH B.Ed	7	15.2	34	73.9	5	10.9
Experience	Up to 5	4	14.8	14	71.9	9	33.3
	6 to 15 years	12	15.4	59	75.6	7	9
	Above15 years	3	5.9	39	76.5	9	17.6

The above table shows that more than three- fifth of special school teachers are having job stress with regard to professional variables namely qualification and experience of the teachers.

H₀1: Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to gender

Table 6

Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to gender

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' Value	P Value
Male	32	52.22	16.12	0.245	0.807 ^{NS}
Female	124	54.49	14.67		

In the above table, since the p value (=0.807) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significant. This shows that there is no significant difference of special school teachers are having job stress with regard to male and female teachers.

While comparing the mean scores of male (52.22) and female (54.49) special school teachers, female special school teachers have higher job stress than male special school teachers.

H₀2: Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to type of family

Table 7

Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to type of family

Family Type	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' Value	P Value
Nuclear	87	55.61	16.01	1.863	0.64 ^{NS}
Joint	69	52.16	13.14		

In the above table, since the p value (=0.64) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significant. This shows that there is no significant difference of special school teachers are having job stress with regard to nuclear and joint family.

While comparing the mean scores of nuclear family (55.22) and joint family (52.16) special school teachers, nuclear family special school teachers have higher job stress than joint family special school teachers.

H₀3: Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to marital status

Table 8

Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to marital status

Marital Status	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' Value	P Value
Married	127	55.41	15.41	1.349	0.179 ^{NS}
Unmarried	29	51.28	12.25		

In the above table, since the p value (=0.179) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significant. This shows that there is no significant difference of special school teachers are having job stress with regard to married and unmarried teachers.

While comparing the mean scores of married teachers (55.41) and unmarried teachers (51.28) special school teachers, married special school teachers have higher job stress than unmarried special school teachers.

H₀ 4: Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to locality

Table 9

Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to locality

Native	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' Value	P Value
Rural	79	50.90	13.26	3.268	0.001*
Urban	77	58.48	15.64		

In the above table, since the p value (= 0.001) is lesser than 0.01, the null hypothesis is not accepted at 1% level of significant. This shows that there is significant difference of special school teachers are having job stress with regard to rural and urban school teachers.

While comparing the mean scores of rural teachers (50.90) and urban teachers (58.48) special school teachers, urban special school teachers have higher job stress than rural special school teachers.

H₀5: Significant of difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to type of school

Table 10

Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to type of school

Type of School	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' Value	P Value
Aided	95	56.85	16.03	2.476	0.014*
Private	61	51.20	12.37		

In the above table, since the p value (=0.14) is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is not accepted at 5% level of significant. This shows that there is significant difference of special school teachers are having job stress with regard to aided and private schools.

While comparing the mean scores of aided (56.85) and private (51.20) special school teachers, aided special school teachers have higher job stress than private special school teachers.

H₀6: Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to qualification

Table 11

Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to qualification

Sources	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	P value
Between Groups	3650.821	1825.410	9.037	0.000*
Within Groups	30905.077	201.994		
Total	34555.897			

In the above table, since the p value (= 0.000) is lesser than 0.01, the null hypothesis is not accepted at 1% level of significant. This shows that there is significant difference among qualification with regard to special school teachers in their job stress.

H₀ 7: Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to experience

Table 1.12

Significant difference in job stress of special school teachers with regard to experience

Sources	Sum of squares	Mean squares	F	P value
Between groups	4088.537	2044.268	10.266	0.000*
Within groups	3467.360	199.133		

Total	34555.897			
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In the above table, since the p value (0.000) is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is not accepted at 1% level of significant. This shows that there is significant difference among special school teachers with regard to experience in their job stress.

Findings

Level of job stress of teachers working in special schools

- More than three-fifth of teachers working in special schools had neutral job stress.
- More than three-fifth of female teachers working in special schools had neutral job stress.
- More than three-fifth of rural teachers working in special schools had neutral job stress
- More than three-fifth of married teachers working in special schools had neutral job stress.
- More than three-fifth of private school teachers working in special schools had neutral job stress.
- More than three-fifth of nuclear family teachers working in special schools had neutral job stress.
- More than three-fifth of PG with B.Ed teachers working in special schools had neutral job stress.
- More than three-fifth of teachers working in special schools with experience up to 5 years had neutral job stress.

Significance of difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools

- There is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to male and female.
- There is significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to rural and urban.
- There is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to married and unmarried.
- There is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to aided and private schools.
- There is no significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to nuclear and joint family.
- There is significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to experience.
- There is significant difference in job stress of teachers working in special schools with regard to qualification.

Recommendations

As a general rule, actions to reduce job stress should be given top priority in the process of organizational change to improve working conditions and to avert the situation of brain drain. But even the most conscientious efforts to improve working conditions are unlikely to eliminate stress completely for all teachers. The stress can be different among different individuals, there by the school management has to identify their problems and it will help to reduce stress. The individuals are to be given enough time to complete their work which would reduce work overload. The individuals are to be given more emphasis on working condition so, that they do their work with interest. Teachers can practice yoga meditation etc. helps to reduce stress and strain. Counseling can be promoted which help a person feel relief from emotional distress which develops more self-assurance, having a greater ability to make decisions and experience an increased comfort in relationship with others. Stress management program should be organized that focuses on different categories of teacher's at all hierarchical level. Job oriented training programs should be introduced which improve teacher's skill and their

confidence to work effectively. Open channel of communication should be encouraged by **organiation** to deal with work related stress. Stress audit should be undertaken at all levels in the organization to identify stress area improving conditions of job and alleviating job stress.

III. Conclusion

This study mainly intends to measure the work culture and job stress of teachers working in special schools. In the changing environment of modern technological advancement the traditional concept teaching profession is subjected to rapid changes. A person who enjoys the work and derives satisfaction alone can perform in the best perfect manner. The fulfillment of personal needs and goals leads to satisfaction wellbeing and happiness. The study helps to find the causes of stress in teachers of special schools and also can be used to reduce the stress by knowing the causes. The study will help for the teacher's wellbeing and in turn student's wellbeing too.

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